

DARBU TENGLAMASI VA UNI YECHISH

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Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada differensial tenglamalarni yechish ko'rsatilgan.

Darbu tenglamasi va uning yechimi keltirilgan

Kalit so'zlar: Differensial, Darbu, Bernulli, tenglama.

Differensial tenglamalar matematikaning muhim bo'limi hisoblanadi. Amaliy hayotga tadbirlarini ko'plab ko'rishimiz mumkin. Differensial tenglamalarni yechish birmuncha qiyin hisoblabadi, ularni chiziqli tenglamaga keltirib yechiladigan Darbu differensial tenglamasini, unga keltiriladigan tenglamalarni va bu tenglamalar bilan bog'liq bo'lgan masalalarni yechish muhim ahamiyatga egadir. Darbu differensial tenglamasi bilan bog'liq tushunchalar, misol va masalalarni o'rganish dolzarbdir.

Ushbu $M(x)dx+N(x)dy+P(x)(xdy-ydx)=0$, (1) ko'rinishdagi tenglamani ham Bernulli differensial tenglamasiga keltirish mumkin, agarda $M(x)$ va $N(x)$ funksiyalar bir o'lchovli va $P(x)$ shu yoki boshqa o'lchovli bir jinsli funksiya bo'lsa. (1) tenglamani ba'zan Darbu tenglamasi deb ham aytiladi.

Faraz qilaylik, $M(x)$ va $N(x)$ ning har biri m -darajali va $P(x)$ esa n -darajali bir jinsli funksiya bo'lsin, ya'ni:

$$M(x) = x^m \varphi_1\left(\frac{y}{x}\right), \quad N(x) = x^m \varphi_2\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) \quad P(x) = x^n \varphi_3\left(\frac{y}{x}\right)$$

Agar $\frac{y}{x} = z$ desak, u holda $y=xz$, $xdy - ydx = x^2 dz$ bo'lib, berilgan (1)

tenglamaning ko'inishi bunday bo'ladi:

$$x^m \varphi_1(z)dx + x^m \varphi_2(z)(xdz + zdx) + x^{n+2} \varphi_3(z)dz = 0 \text{ yoki}$$

$$[\varphi_1(z) + \varphi_2(z)z]dx + [x\varphi_2(z) + x^{n-m+2}\varphi_3(z)]dz = 0 \text{ yoki}$$

$$\frac{dx}{dz} + \frac{\varphi_2(z)x}{\varphi_1(z) + \varphi_2(z)z} + \frac{\varphi_3(z)}{\varphi_1(z) + \varphi_2(z)z} x^{n-m+2} = 0$$

bu esa, Bernulli differensial tenglamasidan iborat bo'lib, bu yerda

$$p(z) = \frac{\varphi_2(z)}{\varphi_1(z) + \varphi_2(z)z}; \quad Q(z) = -\frac{\varphi_3(z)}{\varphi_1(z) + \varphi_2(z)z} \quad \alpha = n - m + 2,$$

$$\frac{dx}{dz} + p(z)x = Q(z)x^\alpha$$

Bu tenglamani esa integrallash mumkin. Albatta integrallashdan so'ng, z ni $\frac{y}{x}$ bilan almashtirish lozimdir.

Misol. Ushbu Darbu tenglamasini integrallang:

$$xy^2 dx + x^3 dy - ay(xdy - ydx) = 0, \quad a = \text{const} \neq 0,$$

Yechilishi: Berilgan tenglamada $m=3, n=1$; shuning uchun $\frac{y}{x} = z$ deb faraz qilamiz bundan,

$$xdy - ydx = x^2 dz$$

demak,

$$x^3 z^2 dx + x^3 (xdz + zdx) - ax^3 z dz = 0 \text{ yoki}$$

buni x^3 ga qisqartirsak, bunday yozish mumkin:

$$(z^2 + z)dx + (x - az)dz = 0, \text{ yoki } \frac{dx}{dz} + \frac{x}{z^2 + z} = \frac{az}{z^2 + z},$$

Bu yerda esa x ga nisbatan birinchi tartibli chiziqli differensial tenglamadan iborat bo'lib,

$P(z) = \frac{1}{z^2 + z}$; $Q(z) = \frac{az}{z^2 + z}$ bu yerda $m=3$, $n=1$ bo'lgani uchun $n-m+2=0$, ya'ni $\alpha=0$ bo'lib, Bernulli tenglamasi birinchi tartibli chiziqli tenglamadan iborat bo'lgan holdir, endi chiziqli tenglamaning umumiy integralining formulasi bo'yicha ushbuni topamiz:

$$x = e^{-\int p(z)dz} \left(\int Q(z)e^{\int p(z)dz} dz + C \right);$$

$$\int p(z)dz = \int \frac{dz}{z^2 + z} = \int \left(\frac{1}{z} + \frac{1}{z+1} \right) dz = \ln|z| - \ln|z+1| = \ln \left| \frac{z}{z+1} \right|;$$

$$e^{-\int p(z)dz} = e^{-\ln \left| \frac{z}{z+1} \right|} = e^{\ln \left| \frac{z+1}{z} \right|} = \frac{z+1}{z};$$

Bu integralni e'tiborga olib umumiy yechimni topamiz:

$$x = \frac{z+1}{z} \left(a \int \frac{zdz}{(z+1)^2} + C \right)$$

$$\frac{z}{(z+1)^2} = \frac{1}{z+1} - \frac{1}{(z+1)^2} \text{ bo'lgani uchun}$$

$$\int \frac{zdz}{(z+1)^2} = \int \frac{dz}{z+1} - \int \frac{dz}{(z+1)^2} = \ln|z+1| - \int (z+1)^{-2} dz = \ln|z+1| - \frac{(z+1)^{-1}}{-1} = \ln|z+1| + \frac{1}{z+1}$$

natijada esa,

$$x = \frac{z+1}{z} \left(a \ln|z+1| + \frac{a}{z+1} + \ln|C_1| \right), \quad C_1 \neq 0 \text{ yoki}$$

$$xz = (z+1) \ln|C_1(1+z)^a| + a;$$

yoki qaytib z ni $\frac{y}{x}$ bilan almashtirilsa

$$(y-a)x = (x+y) \ln \left| \frac{x+y}{x} \right|^a + C_1,$$

$$\left(\frac{x+y}{x} \right)^a C_1 = e^{\frac{(y-a)x}{x+y}}, \quad \frac{x+y}{x} = C_2 e^{\frac{(y-a)x}{(x+y)^a}}, \quad C_2 = \text{const}$$

Shu tariqa $M(x)dx + N(x)dy + P(x)(xdy - ydx) = 0$ ko'rinishidagi differensial tenglamalarni yuqoridagi usul kabi yechish mumkin ekan.

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